

Consumer Behavior

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: August

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Soundharya, P., and
Mahalakshmi B.

“Consumer Behavior.”
*Shanlax International
Journal of Commerce*,
vol. 7, no. S1, 2019,
pp. 68-71.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.3371281](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3371281)

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Abstract

Complementary methods are proposed for understanding and targeting fashion consumers – concentrating primarily on innovation theory, including self-concept theory. Individual is seen as being two potentially relevant suggestions because fashion is concerned with “newness”, therefore innovation theory (also involved with introducing new products and ideas) is logically essential, and because fashion buying could have much to do with extending images of how buyers see themselves (or would like to be seen, etc.) and because there is evidence to recommend that buying in younger markets is related strongly to the representation of self, more than might have been the case in the past. The synthesis of these methods, it is argued, could lead to an increase in fashion branding, based on a greater segmentation of fashion markets. Fashion development, in turn, could be more targeted and use concepts from both innovation and self-concept theory.

Keywords: Innovation Marketing, Consumer behavior, Fashion.

Introduction

As a consumer, we are any unique, and this uniqueness is shown in the consumption pattern and process of purchase. The study of consumer behavior gives us reasons why consumers change one another in buying using products and services. We obtain stimuli from the environment and the specifics of the marketing strategies of various services and products, and responds to these stimuli in terms of either buying or not buying a product.

Objectives

- The terms consumer ‘, customer, ‘ industrial buyer‘ and motives‘
- To Need of consumer behavioral study, differences between organizational buying behavior and consumer buying behavior
- The nature and model of consumer involvement
- Consumer and industrial decision-making process and decision rules
- Marketing implications of consumer behavior
- Study of consumer behavior modeling

Consumer Behaviour

It is broadly the thought of individuals, or organizations and the processes consumers use to select, search, use and dispose of products, services, experience, or ideas to satisfy needs and its impact on the consumer and society.

Customers versus Consumers

The term customers are specific in terms of brand, company, or shop. It refers to a person who customarily or regularly purchases a particular brand, purchases one particular company's product, or purchases from a specific shop. Hence a person who shops at Bata Stores or who uses Raymonds clothing is a buyer of these firms. Whereas the consumers is a person who generally engages in the activities - search, select, use, and disposes of products, services, experience, or ideas.

Consumer Motives

The consumer has a motive for purchasing a particular product. The cause is a strong feeling, urge, instinct, desire, or emotion that makes the buyer decide to buy. Buying motives thus are defined as those considerations or influences which provide the impulse to induce action, buy, either determine choice in the purchase of goods or service.

Motives which Influence Purchase Decision The buying motives may be classified into two:

1. Product Motives
2. Patronage Motives

Product Motives

Product motives may be defined as those impulses, desires, and thoughts which make the buyer purchase a product. These may still be classified based on the nature of satisfaction:

- a) Emotional Product Motives
- b) Rational Product Motives

Emotional Product Motives

Emotional Product Motives are those impulses which satisfy the buyer based on his emotion. The buyer does not try to reflect out or logically analyze the need for purchase. He makes a buying for filling pride, sense of ego, urge to initiate others, and his desire to be unique.

Rational Product Motives

Rational Product Motives are described as those impulses which arise based on logical analysis and proper evaluation. The buyer makes a sensible decision after chief assessment of the purpose, alternatives available, cost-benefit, and such valid reasons.

Patronage Motives

Patronage motives may be described as thought or impulses which persuade the buyer to patronage specific shops, just same product motives patronage can also be grouped as emotional and rational.

Emotional Patronage Motives

Emotional Patronage Motives those that satisfy a customer to buy from specific shops, without any logical reason behind this action. He may be subjective for buying in his favorite place. Rational Patronage Motives are those which appear when selecting an area depending on the user satisfaction that it extends a wide selection, it has the latest models, offers excellent after-sales service, etc.

Need for Study of Consumer Behaviour

The study of consumer behavior encourages everybody, as all are consumers. Marketers must follow consumers to survive and succeed in this competitive marketing environment. The following reasons highlight the effect of studying consumer behavior as a discipline.

Importance in day to day life

The prospect of considering a discipline is to help oneself to appreciate its contributions better. The reason to study consumer behavior is because of the role it plays in the lives of humans. Most of the free time is spent in the shopping, market place, or engaging in other activities. The extra time is usually passed in knowing and creating about products and services, conversing with friends around them, and watching advertisements related to them. The usage of them significantly reveals our lifestyles. All these reasons suggest the need for the study. But, the purpose may be to attend immediate and tangible ideas.

Pertinence to Decision Making

Consumer behavior is said to be an affected discipline, as any decisions are significantly altered by their behavior or expected actions. The two perspectives that seek the application of its knowledge are micro and societal.

Traditional and Modern Theories of Consumer Behavior

The theory is an exposition of the general principles of any science. It is the philosophical explanation of phenomena, either physical or moral. It is a view held or supposition describing something. There are two types of theories that explain consumer behavior - traditional or old theories and modern or contemporary theories.

The traditional theorists would believe that consumers behave mechanistically. Their views of consumers may be connected with that of the economic philosophers' views. Economists explained quite a few principles defining consumer behavior. One of the principles of economics assumes that as consumers' incomes increase, they buy more items for use or consumption. The other law states that, if the supply of an object falls, consumers will go for purchasing that item in more significant quantities meaning an increase of demand. The traditional theorists defining consumer behavior fully accept these economic principles and believed that consumers behave in compliance with financial laws. They thought that consumers are rational creatures, and as a result, every move they take is well thought, planned, and logical. They also applied some of their experiences and intuitions in explaining consumer behavior. Therefore, we can say that traditional theories explaining consumer behaviors were based on economic laws, marketers' own experiences, as well as their intuitions.

The Role of Theory in Science

Consumer behavior theories of modern time are based on empirical results. By practical, we mean, that which is observable as well as measurable. A result may be termed as anecdotal, provided anybody interested may observe it later as well as to measure it. What theory does is that it determines this empirical orientation. The explanation is given by focusing on the data that are needed to explain the theory. You should know that applying a particular method; you do not need to consider all accessible data on the field. Theory tells you which are the relevant data on which you should concentrate on and which you should sidestep.

Data that you consider in using a theory may fall in many categories. If you believe them together without distinguishing them according to their nature, you may lead in the wrong direction.

Theory, you know, is a description of facts. Based on the circumstances, we try to generalize on certain aspects. The generalization should be made in such a way that is supposed empirical. That is, it must have the resources as ‘observability’ and ‘measurability.’ Behind classifying data following a systematic manner, theory reviews them, and based on this; it concludes on the area in question empirically.

The theory considers facts. It is an explanation of events in an orderly manner. Furthermore, it also helps researchers or users to predict effects that one may observe provided the circumstances remain the same. The prediction of facts helps marketers enormously in developing their strategies so that they can combat the competition more effectively.

Criteria of a Sound Theory of Consumer Behaviour

A sound theory of buyer behavior not only defines the practice but also gives a reasonable description of that behavior. Let us say; we have produced a consumer behavior theory on the behavior of female customers of dress materials. In the supposed opinion, it is said that female customers of dress materials enjoy bargaining.

This is a mere description of their behavior, not the description of the behavior. On the contrary, if the theory knows which female customers enjoy agreement, what are the reasons for such a practice, this can be termed as an explanation of behavior. So, a sound theory of buyer behavior describes the behavior, side by side its interpretation.

Conclusion

The study of consumer behavior gives us with reasons why consumers change from one another in buying using products and services. Need of consumer behavioral study, differences within organizational buying behavior and consumer buying. Consumer has a motive for purchasing a particular product behavior. There are two types of theories that describe consumer behavior - the traditional or old methods and modern or contemporary approaches. This consumer behavior is essential marketing.

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